

Effect of N level on leaf B1 intensity and rice yield. Orissa, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Disease intensity ^a (%)	Yield (t/ha)
0	27.19 (31.39)	2.9
40	47.13 (43.35)	3.9
80	60.87 (51.30)	3.1
120	67.54 (55.60)	2.7
160	68.43 (55.82)	2.2
CD (0.05)	7.58	ns
CV (%)	11.43	25.5

^aFigures in the parentheses are angular transformation values.

was higher at higher N levels.

In a trial at RRS, Chiplima, Daya was grown in randomized block design plots with four replications. N levels were 0, 40, 80, 120, and 160 kg/ha. Leaf B1 appeared at maximum tillering during the second wk of Mar, when night temperatures were as low as 15.5–19.5 °C, day temperatures as high as 32.5–36 °C, accompanied by high morning relative humidity of 91.0–96.5. All fully emerged leaves of 20 randomly

selected hills from each plot were examined. Scoring followed the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Disease intensity was calculated:

$$\% \text{ disease intensity} = \frac{\text{sum of disease score} \times 100}{\text{maximum disease score} \times \text{no. of leaves examined}}$$

Disease intensity increased significantly with increased N but differences in grain yield were not significant (see table). □

Purification and serology of ragged stunt virus (RSV)

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RSV was purified from RSV-infected TN1 plants (Omura procedure with some modifications). Plants with roots were homogenized with 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) in 0.01 M MgCl₂. Sap clarified by freezing overnight and defrosting at room temperature was treated with 1% Triton X-100 for 30 min. Virus precipitated with 6% PEG 6000 and 0.3 M sodium chloride was suspended in 0.1 M histidine buffer in 0.01 M MgCl₂ (pH 7.0).

The suspension was treated with 20% CCl₄ and differentially centrifuged. The virus fraction was layered on 20–50% linear sucrose density gradient and centrifuged at 25,000 rev/min for 90 min in a Beckman SW27 rotor.

The zone containing virus particles was recovered with an ISCO Model 640

2. Agar gel diffusion test showing serological relation between RSV in the Philippines and Thailand. The center well contains purified RSV in the Philippines and the outer wells contain antisera to RSV in the Philippines (P) and Thailand (T), and phosphate buffer.

UA5 scanner and centrifuged at 40,000 rev/min for 60 min. The purified virus fraction had maximum UV adsorption

at 260 nm, and UV adsorption ratio at 260 nm and 280 (A_{260/280}) was 1.9–2.1. Purified virus particles were about 60 nm in diameter (Fig. 1).

Five 1-ml aliquots of purified virus fractions, of which A_{260 nm} was adjusted to 1.0, were injected into 2 rabbits at 2-wk intervals. The first four injections were intramuscular, the last injection was intravenous. One week after the last injection, antisera were collected.

The antisera had a titre of 1:1280 in both ring-interface precipitin and double agar gel diffusion tests. In the gel diffusion test, a single band was formed between purified RSV and the antisera, and between RSV and antiserum to RSV from Thailand. The reaction bands fused (Fig. 2), indicating that RSV in the Philippines and in Thailand are serologically indistinguishable. □

1. Electron micrograph of purified RSV negatively stained in 2% uranyl acetate. X100,000.

Timing of planting and variety for rice tungro virus disease (RTV) control

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We studied time of planting and variety relationship to RTV incidence in first and second crop transplanted rice at Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. The first crop was established in Jun, Jul, Aug, and Sep and the second crop in Oct, Nov, Dec, and Jan. Twenty-one-day-old seedlings of IR36, IR42, IR50, IR58, IR64, and TN1 (susceptible

check) were transplanted in 2- × 2-m plots with 20 × 20 cm between hills and 2–3 seedlings/hill. The plants were subjected to natural RTV infection in the field.

At 30 d after transplanting, vector leafhopper populations were estimated by average leafhopper numbers/ 10 sweeps in the plots; RTV-associated virus incidence was determined serologically.

Two leafhopper species, *Nephotettix virescens* and *N. nigropictus*, were present in the area. *N. virescens* was predominant. Fewer than 1 insect/sweep was obtained in plots planted in Jun. Leafhopper catches continued low for

Jul and Aug plantings, but increased for Sep plantings and reached 12 insects/sweep for Oct plantings. The population declined during the relatively cool months of Dec and Jan (Fig. 1).

Incidence of the bacilliform virus (RTBV) and the spherical virus (RTSV) increased with leafhopper populations. Regardless of month of planting, RTSV incidence was present (Fig. 1b). Infection with RTSV alone did not cause RTV symptoms. Dual infection with RTBV and RTSV was observed in Jun, Sep, and Oct plantings. Regardless of month of planting, TN1 was most infected, followed by IR36 and IR42 (Fig. 1c). IR50, IR58, and IR64 were seldom infected. □

Average density of the vector leafhoppers (a) and incidence of RTBV and RTSV (b) at 30 d after transplanting in 6 varieties transplanted monthly from Jun 1985 to Jan 1986; and incidence in each variety regardless of month of transplanting (c).

A scoring system for rice yellow mottle virus disease (RYMV)

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RYMV, an African specific disease of lowland rice varieties, has been studied for its etiology and to screen for resistance. But a standard evaluation system for this disease has not been reported.

The disease is systemic and variable under different growing conditions. Symptoms vary with age of host. Different varieties show different symptoms. Even after repeated inoculations, some immune varieties do not show any virus serologically, even

by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Others with little or no symptoms give positive reactions with ELISA.

The scoring system we propose is compatible with the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Scores are based on leaf color, mottling, plant height, flowering,

Table 2. Differential varieties for RYMV.

Score	Resistance grade	Varieties
0	HR	<i>Oryza glaberrima</i> accessions such as Tog 5612, Tog 5681
2	R	Moroberekan, LAC23
4	MR	OS6, ITA235
7	S	BG90-2, IR5
9	HS	ITA212

and sero-reaction determined by agar-gel diffusion and ELISA techniques. The serological techniques are for restricted use in critical laboratory tests. Most field scores can be based on visual symptoms.

In the score range, 0 represents immunity and 9 extreme susceptibility (death of infected plant) (Table 1).

The actual score range is typified by certain rice varieties which when inoculated display characteristic symptoms (Table 2). □

Table 1. Scoring system for RYMV.

Score	Resistance ^a	Leaf color	Stunting	Flowering	Sero-diagnosis ^b	
					ELISA	Agar-gel diffusion
0	HR	Green	Nil	Normal	-	-
1	R	Green	Nil	Normal	+	±
2	R	Green	Nil	Normal	++	+(weak)
3	R	Green with sparse dots/streaks	Negligible	Normal	+++	+
4	MR	Green with visible mottling	Slight	Normal	+++	++
5	MR	Light green, mottled	25%	Slight delay	Highly positive	
6	S	Pale green	50%	Delayed	Highly positive	
7	S	Pale yellow	75%	Delayed	Highly positive	
8	S	Yellow	>75%	No flowering	Highly positive	
9	HS	Yellow, orange	>75%	Death of plants	Highly positive	

^aHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, and HS = highly susceptible. ^b± = doubtful, - = negative, + = low virus content, ++ = high virus content, +++ = very high virus content.

Crown sheath rot incidence in West Bengal

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Early symptoms of crown sheath rot were reddish brown lesions in patches on the outer leaf sheaths at the crown of the plants. Gradually, the lesions spread throughout the crown sheaths and became dark brown to black. At maturity, clusters of perithecia were produced in the lesions. In severely affected clumps, the culms rotted causing incomplete exsertion and leaf drying (see figure).

Microscopic examination of the rotted crown sheaths showed the